

Title: Socio-demographic factors and Antenatal behaviours of Tribal and non-tribal adolescent mothers: A study from selected districts of Madhya Pradesh

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Abstract

Background: Tribal adolescent mothers in India represent a highly vulnerable group with significantly poorer perinatal outcomes compared to the general population. Socioeconomic and demographic disparities further exacerbate these health inequities.

Objectives: To study the effect of socio-demographic factors associated with tribal and non-tribal adolescent mothers in selected districts of MP

Methods: Community-based cross sectional retrospective study involving tribal & non-tribal adolescent mothers. A pre-tested, structured questionnaire was used to collect data on household factors, reproductive health behaviours, and foetal outcomes

Results: Study involved 177 & 155 respondents from non-tribal and Tribal group from selected districts of Madhya Pradesh. Three-fourths (65.2percent) of tribal respondents had 'No Education', in contrast, respondents in non-tribal group demonstrated relatively higher educational attainment with Primary (31.6percent), followed by middle education (22.6percent). This lack of education is intergenerational and even more pronounced in their parents, with 81.3% of fathers having no education. Critically, their families lacked a stable economic foundation: 51.0% of their fathers and 47.1% of their husbands were 'Unemployed'. This economic and educational vulnerability is compounded by social risk factors. Husbands' alcohol consumption was far higher (87.1percent) in tribal than non-tribal where merely one-thirds of the respondents (33.3percent) husbands consumed alcohol.

Conclusion: Teenage pregnancy is a major public health issue, particularly in low- and middle-income countries such as India, where it significantly increases the burden of maternal and newborn illness. It is a complicated process that results from a combination of biological immaturity and socioeconomic influences. In Madhya Pradesh, where there are many tribal people, cultural traditions, geographical isolation, and disparities in access to healthcare exacerbate the condition of adolescent pregnancy.

Keywords: tribal, adolescent mothers, perinatal outcomes, sociodemographic factors

Introduction: Adolescent pregnancies are a major public health issue, especially in low- and middle-income countries. It impairs a nation's socioeconomic growth and is linked to high rates of maternal and neonatal morbidity and mortality [1]. Teenagers between the ages of 10 and 19 make up about 1 in 6 individuals worldwide. Pregnancy among females between the ages of 10 and 19 is referred to as adolescent pregnancy [2]. Almost 90% of births to women under the age of 20 take place in developing countries accounting for over one-tenth of all births. The lowering age of menstruation and better nutrition and healthier lives of younger generations are the key drivers behind the increased rate of adolescent pregnancy internationally. According to a World Health Organization (WHO) data from 2014, there were 49 births per 1000 girls between the ages of 15 and 19 worldwide [3].

Half of all the teenage births occur in just 7 countries, namely Bangladesh, Brazil, Congo, Ethiopia, Nigeria, India, and USA. As an adolescent girl is not physically mature enough to meet the demands of pregnancy, teenage mothers are more likely to experience pregnancy related complications which can lead to maternal death. Around 70,000 adolescent girls perish each year because of teenage pregnancy [4].

The goal 3 of Sustainable Development Goals by United Nations suggests ensuring healthy lives and promoting well-being for all at all ages. It has a broad target (3.7) of ensuring universal access to sexual and reproductive health-care services, including for family planning, information and education, and the integration of reproductive health into national strategies and programs by 2030. It tracks a specific indicator on adolescent birth rate (aged 10–14 years; aged 15–19 years) per 1,000 women in that age group (Indicator 3.7.2) [5].

As of 2021, the WHO official website estimated the global number of child brides was 650 million, and child marriage places girls at increased risk of pregnancy. Report from UN Women and UNICEF also suggests that around one in every 20 adolescent girls aged 15–19 years around the world (approx. 13 million), have experienced forced sex [6]. Data on WHO official website suggests (as of 2019), adolescents aged 15–19 years in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) had an estimated 21 million pregnancies each year, of which approximately 50 percent were unintended and which resulted in an estimated 12 million births. 55 percent unintended pregnancies among adolescent girls aged 15–19 years end in abortions, which are often unsafe in LMICs [6].

Failure to invest in the health care and proper education of adolescents on the life cycle will further increase the number of dependents in coming generations and negatively influence the health of future generations. It is therefore imperative to work toward improving adolescent health to ensure a brighter future for coming generations. Sustainable development goals provide an opportunity for renewed attention to meeting the health care needs of adolescents through the strengthening of health systems [7].

Materials and Methodology: This study was carried out in Madhya Pradesh which is the second largest state in India and part of Empowered Action Group. A structured questionnaire was prepared for primary data collection. After ensuring reliability and validity it was employed in the target population. All tribal and non-tribal Adolescent mothers were of age 15-19 years delivered in last one year. Age at delivery was less than 20 completed years.

Results: Main respondents of this study were Adolescent mothers from tribal and non-tribal groups. Total number of respondents in non-tribal group is 177 and Tribal group is 155.

Table 1: Age-wise distribution of respondents

Age	Non-Tribal	Tribal	Total
15-19	35 (19.8%)	123 (79.4%)	158 (47.6%)
20-24	142 (80.2%)	32 (20.6%)	174 (52.4%)
Total	177 (100%)	155 (100%)	332 (100%)

Nearly Half of the total respondents (52.4 percent; 174) from both groups, belonged to the 20–24 years age group. Age-wise analysis indicated a contrasting distribution between the two groups. In tribal group, a little more than three-fourths (79.4 percent; 123), of respondents were below 19 years of age.

Among the total respondents from both groups, approx. half of them resided in urban areas (53.6 percent; 174)

Table 2: Distribution of respondents by Place of Residence

Place of Residence	Non-Tribal	Tribal	Total
Urban	104 (58.8%)	74 (47.7%)	178 (53.6%)
Rural	73 (41.2%)	81 (52.3%)	154 (46.4%)
Total	177 (100%)	155 (100%)	332 (100%)

In tribal group, nearly half of the respondents were from rural areas (52.3 percent; 81), compared to the other half (47.7 percent; 74) who were from urban areas. Conversely, in non-tribal group, nearly two-third respondents were urban residents (58.8 percent; 104), while 41.2 percent (73) belonged to rural areas.

Table 3 suggests that majority of respondents belonged to families with seven or more members, accounting for 63.9 percent (212) of the total sample, while 36.1 percent; 120) were from families with four to six members.

Table 3: Distribution of respondents by Number of Family Members

Family Members	Non-Tribal	Tribal	Total
4-6	94 (53.1%)	26 (16.8%)	120 (36.1%)
7 and above	83 (46.9%)	129 (83.2%)	212 (63.9%)
Total	177 (100%)	155 (100%)	332 (100%)

In non-tribal group, more than half of the respondents (53.1 percent; 94) belonged to families with four to six members, whereas nearly the other half of the respondents (46.9 percent; 83) reported family sizes of seven or more members. In contrast, tribal group predominantly comprised respondents from larger families, with 83.2 percent (129) reporting seven or more family members, and only 16.8 percent (26) belonging to families with four to six members.

Table 4 represents overall 38.3 percent of respondents have no formal education, followed by 60.5 percent having any type of school education.

Table 4: Distribution of respondents by Highest Educational Level

Highest educational Level	Non-Tribal	Tribal	Total
No Education	26 (14.7%)	101 (65.2%)	127 (38.3%)
School Education	147 (83%)	54 (34.8%)	25 (60.5%)

Diploma	4 (2.3%)	0 (0%)	4 (1.2%)
Total	177 (100%)	155 (100%)	332 (100%)

Group-wise analysis reveals substantial differences in educational status between the two groups. In tribal group, nearly three-fourths (65.2 percent; 101) of respondents had no formal education, whereas only 14.7 percent of non-tribal group belonged to this category. Conversely majority (83 percent; 147) of non-tribal group had any school education including primary, middle, or secondary.

Table 5 says the largest proportion of husbands had completed primary education, accounting for 42.5 percent (141) of the total sample. This was followed by middle-level education at 22.0 percent (73), secondary education at 13.0 percent (43), and senior secondary education at 10.2 percent (34). A smaller proportion had attained graduation and above (5.1 percent; 17), while only 7.2 percent; 24) had no formal education.

Table 5: Distribution of respondents by Husband's Highest Education Level

Husband's Highest Education Level	Non-Tribal	Tribal	Total
No Education	23 (13%)	1 (0.6%)	24 (7.2%)
Primary	42 (23.7%)	99 (63.9%)	141(42.5%)
Middle	35 (19.8%)	38 (24.5%)	73 (22%)
Secondary	35 (19.8%)	8 (5.2%)	43 (13%)
Senior Secondary	33 (18.7%)	1 (0.6%)	34 (10.2%)
Graduation and above	9 (5%)	8 (5.2%)	17 (5.1%)
Total	177 (100%)	155 (100%)	332 (100%)

Table 6 represents most respondents were unemployed, accounting for 87.0 percent (289) of the total sample, while only 13.0 percent (43) reported being employed

Table 6: Distribution of respondents by Employment Status

Employment Status	Non-Tribal	Tribal	Total
Unemployed	144 (81.4%)	145 (93.5%)	289 (87%)
Employed	33 (18.6%)	10 (6.5%)	43 (13%)
Total	177 (100%)	155 (100%)	332 (100%)

Table 7 represents the distribution of respondents by awareness of modern contraceptive methods across groups. Overall, one-third of respondents (33.7 percent; 112) were aware of modern contraceptive methods, while two-thirds of respondents (66.3 percent; 220) reported no awareness.

Table 7: Awareness of modern contraceptive methods among respondents

Awareness of modern Contraceptive Method	Non-Tribal	Tribal	Total
Yes	101 (57.1%)	11 (7.1%)	112 (33.7%)
No	76 (42.9%)	144 (92.9%)	220 (66.3%)
Total	177 (100%)	155 (100%)	332 (100%)

Group-wise analysis reveals a marked disparity between the two groups. In group non-tribal group, more than half of the respondents (57.1 percent; 101), reported awareness of modern contraceptive methods, less than half (42.9 percent; 76) reported no awareness. In contrast, awareness in tribal

group was extremely low, with only 7.1 percent (11) reporting awareness and an overwhelming 92.9 percent (144) reporting no awareness of modern contraceptive methods.

As mentioned in Table 8, overall, pregnancy registration was evenly distributed between the first and second trimesters. Half of the respondents had their pregnancies registered in the second trimester (50 percent; 166), while 49.7 percent (165) were registered in the first trimester. Registration in the third trimester was negligible, accounting for only 0.3 percent (1).

Table 8: Trimester of Pregnancy registration

Trimester of Pregnancy registration by Health Worker	Non-Tribal	Tribal	Total
First	139 (78.5%)	26 (16.8%)	165 (49.7%)
Second	37 (20.9%)	129 (83.2%)	166 (50%)
Third	1 (0.6%)	0 (%)	1 (0.3%)
Total	177 (100%)	155 (100%)	332 (100%)

Group-wise analysis reveals a marked contrast between the two groups. In non-tribal group, most pregnancies were registered in the first trimester (78.5 percent; 139), followed by the second trimester (20.9 percent; 37), with only one respondent registering in the third trimester (0.6 percent). In contrast, in tribal group, most pregnancies were registered during the second trimester (83.2 percent; 129), while only 16.8 percent (26) were registered in the first trimester, and none in the third trimester.

Table 9 represents, half of the respondents (168) had received two ANC check-ups at the AWC/ field level. This was followed by four or more ANC check-ups among 36.4 percent (121) of respondents. Smaller proportions reported three ANC check-ups (11.4 percent; 38) or only one ANC check-up (1.5 percent; 5).

Table 9: Number of ANC checkups at AWC/Field level

No of ANC Checkups at AWC/ Field level	Non-Tribal	Tribal	Total
None	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
One ANC checkup	3 (1.7%)	2 (1.3%)	5 (1.5%)
Two ANC checkup	35 (19.8%)	133 (85.8%)	168 (50.6%)
Three ANC checkup	32 (18.1%)	6 (3.9%)	38 (11.4%)
Four or more	107 (60.5%)	14 (9%)	121 (36.4%)
Total	177 (100%)	155 (100%)	332 (100%)

Group-wise analysis indicates clear differences between the two groups. In tribal group, most respondents had received two ANC check-ups (85.8 percent; 133), while only 9 percent (14) reported four or more ANC check-ups. In contrast, respondents in non-tribal group reported a higher frequency of ANC visits. In this group, 60.5 percent (107) had received four or more ANC check-ups, followed by two ANC check-ups (19.8 percent; 35) and three ANC check-ups (18.1 percent; 32).

Discussion: In the present study, lack of formal education is a very important socio demographic factor affecting adolescent pregnancy in the tribal population. The Tribal group has a significantly higher proportion of respondents with 'No Education' (65.2 percent) compared to the non-tribal group (14.7 percent). In the study by V Sharma et al, majority of tribal women were illiterate [8] Similarly, Bhattacharjya et al in their study in Tripura found majority of study subjects were illiterates [9]. This finding is a stark illustration of the challenges identified in the literature. It aligns perfectly

with national data from the NFHS-5 (2019-21) [10], which shows the highest rates of early childbearing (18 percent) among women with no schooling. This data also resonates with historical analyses like Chatterjee's (1988) [11] on the low literacy of tribal women and more recent reports, such as by Ravishankar & Ramachandran (2009) [12], on the pervasive poverty and inaccessibility that define many tribal communities.

Tribal families are significantly more likely to have 7 or more members (83.2 percent) compared to non-tribal families (46.9 percent). These results are like the findings of the earlier study by Saha et al [13] where they found 61 percent had family members 6 or more and 80 percent of the aged tribal families had only one earning member. In the present study non-tribal families are much more likely to have 4-6 members (53.1 percent) than Tribal families (16.8 percent).

A study by Minal Madankar et al [14] found that early marriages and traditional practices encouraging pregnancy in adolescence placed tribal girls at risk for adverse pregnancy outcomes. They also remarked that a lack of sexual literacy in tribal adolescents often results in teenage pregnancies with adverse health outcomes. In the present study non-Tribal respondents had significantly more ANC (Antenatal Care) checkups at the AWC/Field level, with 60.5 percent receiving four or more. The Tribal group had significantly fewer checkups at this level, with the vast majority (85.8 percent) receiving only two.

On similar lines, Mudi et al [15] concluded that among the tribal population, the use of contraception is limited and influenced by socio-cultural factors, including existing gender norms. Illiteracy, marriage below 18, younger age, and non-exposure to mass media are significantly associated with the non-use of contraception. This lack of awareness in the tribal group is a well-documented phenomenon. Studies by Sharma et al. (2024) [16], Johnson et al. (2014) [17], and Priyadarshani et al. (2024) [18] all highlight the significant knowledge gaps regarding reproductive health and contraception among tribal adolescents.

The current study, which assessed sociodemographic characteristics antenatal behaviors among adolescent mothers in Madhya Pradesh's, revealed a clear divide between tribal and non-tribal populations. The data demonstrate that adolescent pregnancy is not a single issue, but rather two discrete challenges influenced by disparate factors.

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References:

1. WHO. Adolescents: Health Risks and Solutions. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2017. Available from: <http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs345/en/>
2. Ganchimeg Tet al on behalf of WHO multicountry survey on Maternal Newborn Health Research Network. 2014. "Pregnancy and childbirth outcomes among adolescent mothers: a World Health Organisation multicountry study." BJOG. 2014;121(Suppl 1):40–48. doi: 10.1111/1471-0528.12630.
3. Conde-Agudelo A, Belizán JM, Lammers C. Maternal-perinatal morbidity and mortality associated with adolescent pregnancy in Latin America: cross-sectional study. Am J Obstet Gynecol. 2005;192(2):342-9.
4. Yasmin G, Kumar A, Parihar B. Teenage Pregnancy - Its Impact on Maternal and Foetal Outcome. Int J Sci Study. 2014;1(6):9-13.

5. https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal3#targets_and_indicators accessed on 09 January 2026
6. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/adolescent-pregnancy>; accessed on 01 January 2026.
7. Sully EA, Biddlecom A, Daroch J, Riley T, Ashford L, Lince-Deroche N et al., Adding It Up: Investing in Sexual and Reproductive Health 2019. New York: Guttmacher Institute; 2020.
8. Sharma V, Sharma A. Health profile of pregnant adolescents among selected tribal populations in Rajasthan, India. *J Adolesc Health*. 1992 Dec;13(8):696-9. doi: 10.1016/1054-139x(92)90066-k. PMID: 1290771. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1290771/>
9. Bhattacharjya H, Paul DP, Rakshit AK. Teenage pregnancies, practices, and utilization of RCH services by the tribal and nontribal population of West and South Tripura districts: A mixed method study. *J Family Med Prim Care*. 2021 Aug;10(8):3034-3039. doi: 10.4103/jfmpc.jfmpc_399_21. Epub 2021 Aug 27. PMID: 34660443; PMCID: PMC8483111.
10. National Family Health Survey (NFHS - 5), 2019–21: Government of India- Ministry of Health and Family Welfare: <https://dhsprogram.com/pubs/pdf/FR375/FR375.pdf>
11. Pujasree Chatterjee., Social and Economic status of tribal women in India – The challenges and the Road Ahead- *International Journal of Interdisciplinary and Multidisciplinary Studies (IJIMS)*, 2014, Vol 2, No.2, 55-60. <https://www.ijims.com/uploads/3765dbde1a96580628d3D10.pdf#:~:text=Their%20lack%20of%20ability%20to,helping%20hands%20for%20generating%20income.>
12. Dr. A.K. Ravishankar and Dr. S. Ramachandran., Early Pregnancy And Its Association With Pregnancy-Related Health Problems Among Tribal Young Women In India- <https://ipc2009.popconf.org/papers/90410#:~:text=Three%2Dfourth%20of%20the%20young,consequences%2C%20both%20for%20mother%20and>
13. Joydeb Saha, Sk Nazibar Rahaman, Kazi Monjur Ali, Saheli Ghosal, Subhash Kanti Roy Jagannath Ghosh A study on Demographic profile and Economic status of Aged Tribal People in West Bengal, India *Mukt Shabd Journal* Volume XIV, Issue IV, APRIL/2025 Page No: 503 ISSN NO: 2347-3150
14. Madankar M, Kakade N, Basa L, Sabri B. Exploring Maternal and Child Health Among Tribal Communities in India: A Life Course Perspective. *Glob J Health Sci*. 2024;16(2):31-47. doi: 10.5539/gjhs.v16n2p31. Epub 2024 Jan 4. PMID: 38235348; PMCID: PMC10793648.
15. Mudi, Prasanna Kumar Attitude, and determinants of contraceptive use among the Juang tribe: A cross-sectional study in Odisha, India *Clinical Epidemiology and Global Health*, Volume 24, 101448
16. Sharma, Meena; Engti, Raktim; Mittal, Deepak. Exploring the Perceptions and Challenges of Teenage Pregnancy and Motherhood with Its Way Forward: A Phenomenological Study among the Tribal Population in a Rural Area of Udaipur, Rajasthan, India. *Journal of Primary Care Specialties* 5(2): p 96-101, May–Aug 2024. | DOI: 10.4103/jopcs.jopcs_59_23 https://journals.lww.com/jopcs/fulltext/2024/05020/exploring_the_perceptions_and_challenges_of.4.aspx
17. Johnson LR, Ravichandran M, Thomas MR, Basheer M, Department of Community Medicine, Sree Mookambika Institute of Medical Sciences. Adolescent Reproductive and Sexual Health (ARSH): What do tribal schoolgirls know and do? Vol. VII, *Kerala Medical Journal*. 2014 p. 118. <https://www.keralamedicaljournal.com/index.php/KMJ/article/view/606>
18. Priyadharshani A, Sahoo BK, Mishra A, Singh AK, Parida SP, Panda A. Determinants of teenage pregnancy and knowledge about contraception, sexually transmitted diseases among pregnant women: A case-control study in Eastern India. *J Family Med Prim Care*. 2024 Oct;13(10):4276-

4283. doi: 10.4103/jfmpc.jfmpc_183_24. Epub 2024 Oct 18. PMID: 39629440; PMCID: PMC11610855. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11610855/>